

Microorganisms Translocation from the Colon to Internal Organs under the Influence of Acute Radiation

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Abstract: *During its life, a macroorganism lives in symbiosis with microorganisms located in its biotopes. This mutually beneficial living relationship is established in phylogeny and is formed individually in ontogeny [8, 9, 18]*

The normal microflora located in different biotopes of a person (gastrointestinal system, respiratory system, skin and mucous membranes, urogenital system) participates in the formation and maintenance of the body's immune system, provides a constant antigen stimulus, and ensures an active immune response against antigens. In turn, the immune system plays an important role in the quantitative and qualitative regulation of representatives of normal microflora in different biotopes [3, 11, 14, 17].

As a result of various external and internal influences, when the balance of normal microflora representatives (indigenous and facultative microflora) in the human colon is disturbed, the permeability of the intestinal mucosa increases, the transfer (translocation) of viable microorganisms to various internal organs increases [7, 13, 15]. In this case, there are changes in the transient bacteremia observed in healthy people, and there is information about the intensification of this process [11, 19].

Although a lot of work has been done on the mechanism of translocation of microorganisms to internal organs as a result of various external and internal influences, their variability, pre-pathology and pathological conditions caused in the body [1, 7, 9, 13, 15], the role of the immune system in this process has not been sufficiently revealed. . Therefore, it is appropriate to continue experimental studies to evaluate the role of the immune system in the process of translocation of microorganisms to internal organs.

The purpose of the study. The percentage of microorganisms translocated from the large intestine to the internal organs in the dynamics under the influence of acute radiation was studied experimentally.

Research material and methods. A total of 162 male white mice were included in the research. Their weight was not less than 25 g, and their age was 3 months.

All laboratory animals were divided into 3 groups:

Group 1 - non-white mice that received acute radiation (n=54);

Group 2 - white mice without acute radiation and preventive biocorrection (n=54);

Group 3 - intact mice without acute radiation (n=54).

Care, feeding, grouping of laboratory animals was carried out using traditional methods [10]. Ethical principles of working with laboratory animals and biological safety rules were strictly observed [2, 4, 10]. All laboratory animals were kept in quarantine for 10 days before the experiment.

Acute irradiation of laboratory animals was carried out using the AGAT-R1 (Estonia, 1991) g-therapeutic apparatus, where the radiation source was So-60. Studies related to acute irradiation of laboratory animals were conducted at the Bukhara branch of the Republican Scientific and Practical Center of Oncology and Radiology.

White mice that received acute radiation were kept on a common vivarium diet until the 5th day, from the day of irradiation, laboratory animals of the 2nd group were treated with prophylactic biocorrection with "Lactopropolis-AWL" produced in our country. Group 1 and 3 animals were kept only on vivarium diet.

The biologically active supplement Lactopropolis-AWL was given daily in the morning based on the weight of all laboratory animals. Acutely irradiated subjects were given the drug for 20 days, irradiated on the last day, and then euthanized on day 5 and studied.

"Lactopropolis-AWL" biologically active supplement consists of extracts of *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* 925, *Enterococcus durans* probiotic bacteria and biologically active compounds of propolis, it has antimicrobial, immunostimulating, anti-inflammatory properties (a product of the Institute of Microbiology of the Federal Republic of Uzbekistan and "AllWellLab" LLC).

After irradiation, on the 5th, 7th and 9th days of the experiment, the laboratory animals were euthanized, and bacteriological studies were continued by taking samples from the internal organs "print-smear" and Gold.

Extensive bacteriological studies were conducted on microorganisms grown from biological materials obtained from mesenteric lymph nodes, liver, spleen, lungs and peripheral blood of laboratory animals. Identification was performed according to Bergys Manual of Systematic Bacteriology (1997). For bacteriological tests, nutrient media from the company "HiMedia" (India) were used.

Since the main task in this research work is to determine the percentage of microorganisms translocated from the large intestine to internal organs, only the genera of microorganisms capable of translocation were identified - *Escherichia* spp, *Proteus* spp, *Staphylococcus* spp, *Enterococcus* spp, *Bacteroides* spp [5, 6, 12]. Due to the small importance of species in the passage of microorganisms from the large intestine to the internal organs, they were identified only to the genus.

Traditional variational statistics methods were used for statistical processing of the results. Arithmetic average quantity (M), average quantity error (m) and reliability criterion (t) were determined in it. All checks were carried out using Excel software on personal computers with Pentium-IV processor. The principles of evidence-based medicine were used in the organization and conduct of research.

The obtained results and their discussion. In the experiment, the percentage of microorganisms translocated from the large intestine to the mesenteric lymph nodes of laboratory animals was different from each other in all three groups in the dynamics of observation (Table 1).

If in group 1, on the 5th day after irradiation, the percentage of microorganisms translocated from the colon was $88.89 \pm 7.41\%$ (in 16 out of 18), by the 7th day, this indicator reached $93.75 \pm 6.05\%$ increased (in 15 out of 16 cases). On the 9th day after irradiation, translocation reached a maximum level - 100.0% (in 12 out of 12 cases).

It can be seen that the percentage of translocated microorganisms increased dynamically after irradiation.

Table 1 Indicators of the dynamics of the percentage of encounters of microorganisms with translocation from the large intestine to the mesenteric lymph nodes after acute radiation in the experiment

Groups	Post-irradiation period	Results	
		Absolutely	%
Group 1 (received acute radiation), n =54	Day 5, n= 18	16	88.89±7.41
	Day 7, n= 16	15	93.75±6.05
	Day 9, n= 12	12	100.0
Group 2 (acute radiation + prophylactic biocorrection), n =54	Day 5, n= 18	15	83.33±8.78
	Day 7, n= 17	13	76.47±10.29
	Day 9, n= 16	9	56.25±12.40
Group 3 (no acute irradiation, control), n =54	Day 5, n= 18	1	5.56±5.40
	Day 7, n= 18	0	0
	Day 9, n= 18	1	5.56±5.40

In the 2nd group of laboratory animals (acute radiation + prophylactic biocorrection), we observed the opposite. Over time, the percentage of microorganisms from the mesenteric lymph nodes decreased - 83.33±8.78% on the 5th day (in 15 out of 18); 76.47±10.29% (13 out of 17) on day 7 and 56.25±12.40% (16 out of 18) on day 9.

However, no changes were observed in group 3 (intact) during the observation period. Microorganisms with translocation did not exceed 5.56±5.40% (in 1 out of 18), their increase or decrease trend was not observed.

Analysis of the results showed that acute radiation increased the permeability of the colonic mucosa, as the percentage of microorganisms encountered in other groups (received acute radiation) compared to the control group (did not receive acute radiation) increased dramatically ($R < 0.001$). Over time, the percentage of encounters in group 1 increased and reached a maximum (100%) by the end of the observation period (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Indicators of the percentage of germination of microorganisms translocated from the large intestine to the mesenteric lymph nodes of laboratory animals, %

The positive effect of per os biocorrection of laboratory animals until the 5th day was revealed when comparing groups 1 and 2. So, acute radiation caused signs of dysbiosis in the large intestine, decreased indigenous microorganisms, and increased facultative strains. When trying to restore this balance with

the help of prophylactic biocorrection, the decrease in translocation was determined as a result of the decrease in the percentage of microorganisms encountered during the observation period.

Another point is that in group 1, the mortality rate of laboratory animals on the 7th day of the experiment was 11.11% (n=2), while in group 2 it was 5.56% (n=1), with the passage of time (9th day) mortality in group 1 reached 33.33% (n=6), while mortality in group 2 It was 11.11% (n=2). Comparative analysis allowed us to interpret that the decrease in mortality is a positive effect of biocorrection. No mortality was observed in the control group.

Thus, after acute irradiation in laboratory animals, the percentage of germination of microorganisms that passed from the large intestine to the mesenteric lymph nodes increased and reached 100.0% on the 9th day after irradiation. Biocorrected, irradiated laboratory animals also had a high percentage of microorganism germination, but in the dynamics of observation, their percentage decreased and decreased to 56.25% on the last 9 days after irradiation. In the control group, these patterns were not observed, and the percentage did not exceed 5.56%. Notably, while all control (unirradiated) animals survived during the observation period, irradiated mice continued to die over time, and by day 9 the mortality rate was 33.33% in group 1 and 11.11% in group 2.

Experimental and microbiological studies similar to the above were also conducted with the liver of laboratory animals.

The rate of germination of microorganisms from the liver of laboratory animals was similar to the parameters of mesenteric lymph nodes - it was related to the tendency and intensity of growth of the percentage of germination during the observation period.

Indicators of germination of microorganisms translocated from the large intestine to the liver increased dynamically during the observation period - 83.33±8.78% on day 5 in group 1, respectively; 93.75±6.05% on day 7 and 100.0% on day 9 (Table 2).

Table 2 Indicators of the dynamics of the percentage of microorganisms that passed from the large intestine to the liver after acute radiation in the experiment

Groups	Post-irradiation period	Results	
		Absolutely	%
Group 1 (received acute radiation), n =54	Day 5, n= 18	15	83.33±8.78
	Day 7, n= 16	15	93.75±6.05
	Day 9, n= 12	12	100.0
Group 2 (acute radiation + prophylactic biocorrection), n =54	Day 5, n= 18	14	77.78±9.80
	Day 7, n= 17	13	70.59±11.05
	Day 9, n= 16	8	50.0±12.50
Group 3 (no acute irradiation, control), n =54	Day 5, n= 18	0	0
	Day 7, n= 18	0	0
	Day 9, n= 18	1	5.56±5.40

The trend and intensity of changes in laboratory animals of group 2, where biocorrection was applied, were practically the same as in mesenteric lymph nodes - 77.78±9.80% (in 14 out of 18) on the 5th day, respectively; 70.59±11.05% (12 out of 17) on day 7 and 50.0±12.50% (6 out of 12) on day 9. The

positive effect of biocorrection is also evident from the fact that the parameters of groups 1 and 2 are inversely proportional to each other (Fig. 2).

Thus, the analysis of germination parameters in the liver of microorganisms that passed through the large intestine of experimentally irradiated laboratory animals showed that after irradiation, the germination percentage tended to increase with time, but the intensity of reproduction was lower than the parameters of mesenteric lymph nodes. In irradiated, biocorrected laboratory animals, the results were inversely proportional. This is due to the fact that biocorrection reduces the negative effect of radiation on the normal microflora of the large intestine. The parameters of both groups of irradiated laboratory animals were significantly different from those of the control group due to the negative effect of radiation on the immune system and through it on the normal microflora of the large intestine.

Figure 2. In the experiment, indicators of germination of microorganisms that passed through the large intestine of laboratory animals from their liver, %

The next stage of scientific work was to study the percentage of germination of microorganisms that passed through the large intestine in the spleen of irradiated laboratory animals using bacteriological methods. On the 5th day after a single (acute) irradiation, microorganisms were recovered from the spleen of group 1 animals in $72.22 \pm 10.56\%$ of cases (12 out of 18 cases) (Table 3).

On the 7th and 9th days of the experiment, this indicator had a tendency to increase - $81.25 \pm 9.76\%$ (in 13 out of 16) and 100% (in all), respectively.

Germination of microorganisms was also observed in the spleen of group 2 laboratory animals that received acute radiation and received prophylactic biocorrection. This germination had the characteristic of decreasing over time - $72.22 \pm 10.56\%$ on the 5th day (in 13 out of 18); $64.71 \pm 11.59\%$ (11 out of 17) on day 7 and $43.75 \pm 12.40\%$ (7 out of 16) on day 9. Microorganisms did not germinate in the spleen of intact laboratory animals included in the control group (0%).

Table 3 Indicators of the dynamics of the percentage of microorganisms that passed from the large intestine to the spleen after acute radiation in the experiment

Groups	Post-irradiation period	Results	
		Absolutely	%
Group 1 (received acute radiation), n =54	Day 5, n= 18	13	72.22±10.56
	Day 7, n= 16	13	81.25±9.76
	Day 9, n= 12	12	100.0
Group 2 (acute radiation + prophylactic biocorrection), n =54	Day 5, n= 18	13	72.22±10.56
	Day 7, n= 17	11	64.71±11.59
	Day 9, n= 16	7	43.75±12.40
Group 3 (no acute irradiation, control), n =54	Day 5, n= 18	0	0
	Day 7, n= 18	0	0
	Day 9, n= 18	0	0

Although the percentage of microorganisms grown from the lungs of irradiated and non-irradiated laboratory animals was distinguished by a decrease in intensity compared to other organs (mesenteric lymph nodes, liver, spleen), the trend of changes was the same (Table 4).

It was found that the percentage of microorganisms that grew in the lungs during the observation period in group 1 laboratory animals from the day of irradiation increased from 55.56±11.71% (10 out of 18) on the 5th day to 91.67±7.98% (12 out of 18) on the 9th day. in 11 of them) increased.

Also, in group 2, the percentage of translocation of colonic microorganisms in the lungs of laboratory animals decreased over time - from 61.11±11.49% on the 5th day (11 out of 18) to 37.5±12.10 on the 9th day. to % (in 6 out of 16). No fever was observed in the control group.

Table 4 Indicators of the dynamics of the percentage of microorganisms that passed from the large intestine to the lungs after acute radiation in the experiment

Groups	Post-irradiation period	Results	
		Absolutely	%
Group 1 (received acute radiation), n =54	Day 5, n= 18	10	55.56±11.71
	Day 7, n= 16	12	75.0±10.83
	Day 9, n= 12	11	91.67±7.98
Group 2 (acute radiation + prophylactic biocorrection), n =54	Day 5, n= 18	11	61.11±11.49
	Day 7, n= 17	9	52.94±12.11
	Day 9, n= 16	6	37.5±12.10
Group 3 (no acute irradiation, control), n =54	Day 5, n= 18	0	0
	Day 7, n= 18	0	0
	Day 9, n= 18	0	0

Thus, the percentage of germination of microorganisms translocated from the colon in the spleen and lungs of laboratory animals ranged from $37.5\pm 12.10\%$ to 100.0% in irradiated mice, while no germination was observed in non-irradiated mice. In irradiated animals, the percentage of microorganism germination increased over time, while in irradiated, biocorrected animals, the percentage of germination decreased. Taking into account that this trend was also observed in mesenteric lymph nodes, liver and spleen, we can be sure that the dynamics of the percentage of germination of translocated microorganisms in all organs is practically the same.

In all cases, in irradiated laboratory animals (regardless of biocorrection or not), we observed the ability of microorganisms to pass from the large intestine to the internal organs. In our opinion, this is the result of not only total immunodeficiency, increased permeability of the colon mucosa, but also profound dysbiotic changes in the microbiocenosis of the colon. This pathogenetic mechanism was recognized as the factor causing the ability of microorganisms to enter the internal organs and its intensity.

After studying and describing the dynamics of germination percentages of microorganisms that passed through the large intestine in the internal organs, we considered that it is necessary to study the germination indicators of these strains in the peripheral blood of experimental animals.

In the peripheral blood of irradiated laboratory animals, their clotting tendencies remained unchanged (Table 5).

Table 5 Indicators of the percentage of microorganisms that passed from the large intestine to the peripheral blood after acute radiation in the experiment

Groups	Post-irradiation period	Results	
		Absolutely	%
Group 1 (received acute radiation), n =54	Day 5, n= 18	11	61.11 ± 11.49
	Day 7, n= 16	12	75.0 ± 10.83
	Day 9, n= 12	10	83.33 ± 10.76
Group 2 (acute radiation + prophylactic biocorrection), n =54	Day 5, n= 18	11	61.11 ± 11.49
	Day 7, n= 17	10	58.82 ± 11.94
	Day 9, n= 16	7	43.75 ± 12.40
Group 3 (no acute irradiation, control) , n =54	Day 5, n= 18	1	5.56 ± 5.40
	Day 7, n= 18	2	11.11 ± 7.41
	Day 9, n= 18	1	5.56 ± 5.40

According to the previous results, after irradiation during the observation period in group 1, the percentage of germination of strains increased over time - $61.11\pm 11.49\%$ on the 5th day (11 out of 18); $75.0\pm 10.83\%$ (12 out of 16) and $83.33\pm 10.76\%$ (10 out of 12) on day 7. In group 2, it was the opposite, i.e., the percentage of germination decreased with time.

A different feature from the studied internal organs is that in the non-irradiated animals of the control group, strain germination was observed during the observation period - from $5.56\pm 5.40\%$ to $11.11\pm 7.41\%$ (in 1 or 2 out of 18).

Thus, the percentage of microorganisms that passed through the colon from the peripheral blood of acutely irradiated laboratory animals increased as the observation period increased. In biocorrected, irradiated animals, the percentage of microorganism germination decreased over time. In both groups,

the indicators of microorganism germination were significantly higher than the parameters in the control group.

Conclusions

1. The percentage of micro-organisms in the mesenteric lymph nodes of white mice that received acute radiation increased and reached 100.0% on the 9th day after radiation.
2. In laboratory animals that underwent prophylactic biocorrection and received acute radiation, the percentage of translocation strains was also high, but in the dynamics of observation, their percentage decreased and decreased to 56.25% on the last 9 days after acute radiation
3. In laboratory animals in the control group that did not receive acute radiation, there were no laws related to the translocation of microorganisms, and the percentage of germination did not exceed 5.56%.
4. The lethality increased among irradiated mice, and by day 9 the mortality rate was 33.33% in group 1 and 11.11% in group 2, while all acutely irradiated animals survived during the follow-up period.
5. In laboratory animals that received acute radiation in the experiment, the indicators of germination of the strains of microorganisms translocated from the large intestine of the liver tended to increase over time, but the intensity of reproduction was lower than the parameters of the mesenteric lymph nodes. The results of laboratory animals that received acute radiation and underwent prophylactic biocorrection were inversely proportional to those of group 1. It was interpreted that this is related to the reduction of the negative effect of radiation on the normal microflora of the large intestine.
6. In the spleen and lungs of irradiated laboratory animals, the percentage of microorganisms translocated from the large intestine was a parameter ranging from 37.5±12.10% to 100.0%. Germination percentage decreased in irradiated, biocorrected animals. Taking into account that this trend was also observed in mesenteric lymph nodes, liver and spleen, the dynamics of the percentage of microorganisms with translocation in all organs was practically the same.
7. The percentage of microorganisms passing through the colon from the peripheral blood of irradiated laboratory animals increased as the observation period increased. In biocorrected, irradiated animals, the percentage of microorganism germination decreased over time. In both groups, its values were significantly higher than those in the control group.

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